

Performance Analysis Of Hydrogen Enriched Petrol Engine

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Abstract

Crisis of fossil fuel and environmental degradation shift around the world to cleaner and more convenient forms of energy and resulting efficiency gains help moderate the increase in commercial and residential demand. Particularly in developing countries, these gains are helping improve the quality of life, while mitigating health problems.

Experimental results showed lower exhaust emissions and improved performance using dual fuel mode with hydrogen as substitute fuel. It was also found that hydrogen enriched engine gives maximum efficiency.

The reason for reduction in BSEC may be the homogeneous mixing of hydrogen in the combustion chamber resulting in improved combustion. The overall performance of hydrogen is comparable to that of Diesel. It can therefore be concluded that hydrogen is a good alternate fuel for future.

Project aims to investigate the performance characteristics of hydrogen-enriched petrol engines, offering insights into their potential as a sustainable alternative in the automotive industry. Through comprehensive experimental testing and computational simulations, this study evaluates key performance parameters such as power output, speed of vehicle, mileage, fuel efficiency, hydrogen conversion rate, and emissions profiles of hydrogen-enriched petrol engines.

Keywords— Hydrogen, Exhaust emissions, Petrol engine, Improved Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of sustainable energy solutions has become increasingly imperative in mitigating environmental concerns and addressing the challenges posed by conventional fossil fuel consumption in the automotive industry. Hydrogen-enriched petrol engines have emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing engine performance while reducing emissions.

The concept of hydrogen-enriched petrol engines revolves around blending hydrogen gas with traditional petrol fuel to create a hybrid fuel mixture. Through a combination of experimental testing and computational simulations, this study aims to provide a thorough understanding of how hydrogen enrichment influences key engine parameters such as power output, fuel consumption, combustion stability, and emissions profiles.

Numerous experimental studies have been conducted to analyse the performance of hydrogen-enriched petrol engines. Computational models and simulations are widely used to analyse the performance of hydrogen enriched petrol engines. These model help researchers understand the complex interaction between hydrogen and petrol combustion, optimize engine design, operating conditions and predict performance outcomes.

In an era defined by environmental consciousness and the quest for sustainable energy solutions, HHO generation stands out as a beacon of hope for a cleaner, greener future. At its core, HHO generation

harnesses the power of water to produce hydrogen and oxygen gases through the process of electrolysis. These gases, collectively known as Brown's gas or HHO, possess remarkable potential to revolutionize the way we consume and generate energy.

The journey towards HHO generation begins with a simple premise: water, the most abundant compound on Earth, can be transformed into a clean and renewable source of fuel. By applying an electric current to water molecules, electrolyzers split them into their constituent elements: hydrogen and oxygen. This elegant process mimics nature's own mechanism of water splitting during photosynthesis, but with one crucial difference – it can be harnessed and controlled by human ingenuity.

The resulting HHO gas, a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen in precise proportions, holds immense promise across a spectrum of applications. From powering vehicles to supplementing industrial processes and even providing off-grid energy solutions for residential use, the versatility of HHO technology knows no bounds. But beyond its practical applications lies a deeper significance – the potential to reduce our dependence on fossil fuels and mitigate the environmental impact of traditional energy sources.

HHO generation represents a paradigm shift in the way we approach energy production and consumption. Unlike fossil fuels, which emit harmful greenhouse gases when burned, HHO combustion produces only water vapor as a byproduct, making it a truly clean and sustainable energy source. This attribute alone holds profound implications for combating climate change and preserving the health of our planet for future generations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

A study by F. Amrouche, P. Erickson, J. Park, and S. Varnhagen investigated the effects of adding hydrogen to gasoline fuel in a Wankel rotary engine. Their research, titled "An experimental investigation of hydrogen enriched gasoline in a Wankel rotary engine," found that a 10% energy fraction of hydrogen enrichment resulted in a 20% improvement in the engine's brake thermal efficiency compared to using just gasoline. This improvement translates to benefits like: Increased Fuel Efficiency: The engine consumed less fuel to produce the same amount of power, as indicated by the decrease in brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC). Reduced Emissions: A cleaner and more efficient burn suggests potentially lower emissions of pollutants.

Cooler Engine Operation: The decrease in exhaust temperature implies cleaner and potentially more complete combustion. Potential for Further Improvement and Challenges While the study shows promise, some considerations remain: Optimal Hydrogen Ratio: The 10% enrichment ratio used might not be ideal for all engines or conditions. Further research is needed to determine the best range for maximum benefit. Hydrogen Infrastructure: Widespread adoption would depend on the availability and affordability of hydrogen as a fuel source. Overall, this research demonstrates that hydrogen enrichment has the potential to significantly improve the performance and efficiency of Wankel rotary engines. Further studies can optimize the technology and explore its broader applicability. [1]

Researchers Baiju B, Gokul S, Sachin Sunny, Ranjith C. M, and Sathyamoorthy U explored the potential of hydrogen-petrol mixtures in Spark Ignition (SI) engines. Their study, titled "Hydrogen Petrol mixture

SI engine," involved testing a hydrogen-petrol mix on a test rig and a two-wheeler. In both cases, they observed a significant decrease in fuel consumption. This finding suggests two potential benefits:

Increased Engine Power: The reduced fuel consumption could translate to more power output from the engine. Essentially, the engine might be burning fuel more efficiently due to the presence of hydrogen.

Improved Mileage: Another possibility is that the engine achieves the same power output while consuming less fuel. This would lead to better fuel economy and potentially longer driving range.

While the study offers promising results, further research is needed to determine the ideal hydrogen-to-petrol ratio for optimal performance and efficiency. Additionally, widespread adoption would depend on the development of a cost-effective hydrogen infrastructure. Overall, this study paves the way for further exploration of hydrogen enrichment as a method to improve the performance and efficiency of SI engines.[2]

A review by Behdad Shadidi, Gholamhassan Najafi, and Talal Yusuf titled "A review of hydrogen as a fuel in Internal Combustion engine" examined the impact of hydrogen addition on engine performance. Their findings suggest a trade-off

Reduced Emissions: The study acknowledges potential benefits for emissions when using hydrogen as an additive in Spark Ignition (SI) and Compression Ignition (CI) engines.

Power and Torque Loss: However, the review highlights a downside - a decrease in volumetric efficiency. This can lead to a reduction in engine power and torque output. This highlights the complex relationship between hydrogen and engine performance. While it might offer environmental advantages, further research is needed to address the power and torque drawbacks before widespread adoption. [3]

A study by Seyed Ehsan Hosseini & Brayden Butler, titled "An overview of development and challenges in hydrogen powered vehicles," highlights the potential and limitations of hydrogen technology.

Hydrogen Engines Offer Efficiency Gains: Compared to traditional gasoline-powered engines (ICEs), hydrogen-powered engines (H2ICEs) can achieve significantly higher efficiency, ranging from 20-25%. This translates to cleaner fuel consumption and potentially lower emissions.

Challenges Hinder H2ICE Adoption: Despite the efficiency advantage, technical hurdles currently limit the widespread use of H2ICEs.

Hydrogen as a Transitional Solution: Due to these challenges, researchers are exploring the use of hydrogen as an additive to existing hydrocarbon fuels. This approach offers a potential transitional strategy for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in transportation engines while addressing the limitations of H2ICEs directly. [4]

Harman de Vriese, Anatoli V. Mokhov, and Howard B. Levinsky conducted an interchangeability analysis to assess the effects of adding hydrogen to natural gas. They found that the performance of end-use equipment, such as domestic appliances, is influenced by the composition of the natural gas and the amount of hydrogen added. The results demonstrate that there is a maximum level of hydrogen admixture that can be added without negatively affecting performance.[5]

HHO Generator

The environmental imperative of reducing carbon emissions and mitigating air pollution is a central focus of HHO generation. Traditional fossil fuels, such as coal, oil, and natural gas, contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants, exacerbating global warming and threatening public health. By contrast, HHO combustion produces only water vapor as a byproduct, ensuring clean combustion and minimizing environmental impact. This clean burning process not only reduces carbon emissions but also mitigates the harmful effects of pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter, thereby safeguarding ecosystem health and fostering sustainable development.

Beyond environmental considerations, HHO generation offers compelling economic advantages, particularly in the realm of transportation and industrial operations. In the automotive sector, HHO technology enhances fuel combustion and mileage in vehicles, leading to reduced fuel consumption and lower operating costs. By augmenting conventional fuels with HHO gas, engines achieve more complete combustion, resulting in improved engine efficiency and optimized performance. This increased efficiency translates into tangible cost savings for consumers and fleet operators, making HHO-powered vehicles an attractive option in an era of fluctuating fuel prices and economic uncertainty.

1. Electrolyzer:

The electrolyzer stands as the cornerstone of the HHO generation kit, responsible for the fundamental process of electrolysis. This core component harnesses electrical energy to induce a chemical reaction within a water-based solution, thereby splitting water molecules (H₂O) into their constituent elements: hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂) gases. Operating on the principle of electrochemistry, the electrolyzer typically consists of electrodes submerged in an electrolyte solution. These electrodes serve as catalysts, facilitating the transfer of electrons and ions during the electrolysis process. As electricity flows through the electrolyte, water molecules undergo decomposition, yielding hydrogen at the cathode and oxygen at the anode.

2. Reservoir:

The reservoir serves as the storage unit for the produced HHO gas, ensuring a reliable and steady supply of hydrogen and oxygen for various applications. This crucial component plays a pivotal role in maintaining operational continuity, allowing HHO gas to be stored for later use or distributed as needed. The size and capacity of the reservoir can vary depending on the intended application of the HHO system, ranging from small-scale residential setups to industrial-scale installations. By storing HHO gas under controlled conditions, the reservoir enhances safety and facilitates efficient utilization of the generated gases.

3. Control System:

The control system serves as the brain of the HHO generation kit, overseeing and regulating the entire process of gas production. Comprising a suite of sensors, actuators, and control algorithms, this sophisticated component ensures precise control over HHO production rates and gas flow dynamics. By monitoring key parameters such as electrolyzer performance, gas pressure, and temperature, the control system optimizes system efficiency and safeguards against potential hazards. Moreover, the control system facilitates seamless integration with existing infrastructure and enables remote monitoring and control capabilities, enhancing operational flexibility and user convenience.

4. Installation Accessories:

The installation accessories encompass a range of components essential for the proper assembly and integration of the HHO generation kit. Hoses serve as conduits for transporting HHO gas between the electrolyzer, reservoir, and other system components, ensuring efficient gas flow and distribution. Connectors play a crucial role in joining different parts of the HHO system securely, forming leak-tight seals and minimizing gas loss. Meanwhile, mounting hardware provides sturdy attachment points for securing the electrolyzer and reservoir to vehicles, structures, or other surfaces, ensuring stable and reliable operation under diverse operating conditions.

5. Electrolyte:

The electrolyte constitutes a vital component of the electrolyzer, facilitating the electrolysis process and enhancing overall system performance. Typically composed of water (H₂O) and a soluble substance such as potassium hydroxide (KOH) or sodium hydroxide (NaOH), the electrolyte serves multiple functions. Firstly, it provides a conductive medium for the flow of electrical current, enabling efficient ionization and transport of ions within the electrolyzer. Additionally, the electrolyte facilitates chemical reactions at the electrode surfaces, promoting the dissociation of water molecules and the generation of hydrogen and oxygen gases. By carefully selecting and maintaining the electrolyte composition, operators can optimize electrolyzer efficiency and prolong system lifespan.

The working of electrolysis with a catalyst, examining the underlying equations and key points.

1. Electrolysis Process:

Electrolysis of water involves the passage of an electric current through an electrolyte solution, typically comprising water and a catalyst. The electrolysis cell consists of two electrodes – a cathode (negative electrode) and an anode (positive electrode) – immersed in the electrolyte solution.

2. Cathodic Reaction:

At the cathode, where reduction occurs, water molecules (H₂O) are reduced to hydrogen gas (H₂) and hydroxide ions (OH⁻). This reduction reaction is represented by the equation.

3. Anodic Reaction:

At the anode, where oxidation occurs, hydroxide ions (OH⁻) are oxidized to oxygen gas (O₂), water (H₂O), and electrons. This oxidation reaction is represented by the equation:

4. Overall Reaction:

The overall reaction of electrolysis of water, in the presence of a catalyst, yields hydrogen gas and oxygen gas. The combined cathodic and anodic reactions can be represented by the overall equation:

5. Catalyst Functionality:

The catalyst, such as potassium hydroxide (KOH) or sodium hydroxide (NaOH), plays a crucial role in facilitating the electrolysis process. It acts as a promoter, accelerating the dissociation of water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen ions. By lowering the activation energy barrier for the reaction, the catalyst enables faster and more efficient electrolysis, thereby reducing the energy input required.

6. Mechanism of Catalysis:

The presence of the catalyst alters the reaction pathway, providing an alternative route for the transformation of reactants into products. In the case of electrolysis with a catalyst, the catalyst molecules adsorb onto the surface of the electrodes, enhancing the interaction between water molecules and facilitating the transfer of electrons and ions. This enhanced interaction promotes the breaking of chemical bonds within the water molecules, leading to the formation of hydrogen and oxygen gases.

7. Benefits of Catalysts:

The incorporation of a catalyst in the electrolysis process offers several benefits:

- Increased reaction rate: Catalysts accelerate the rate of reaction, leading to faster HHO gas generation.
- Reduced energy requirements: The catalytic activity lowers the energy input needed for electrolysis, making the process more energy-efficient.
- Enhanced efficiency: By promoting the dissociation of water molecules, catalysts improve the overall efficiency of HHO generation, maximizing gas yield per unit of electricity consumed.

In summary, the electrolysis of water in HHO generation with a catalyst is a complex yet highly efficient process. Through a series of chemical reactions at the cathode and anode, water molecules are split into hydrogen and oxygen gases. The presence of a catalyst, such as potassium hydroxide or sodium hydroxide, enhances the efficiency of electrolysis by lowering the energy barrier and facilitating faster reaction rates. This catalytic promotion of electrolysis holds immense promise for advancing the development of clean and renewable energy technologies, paving the way towards a sustainable future.

3. CALCULATIONS

$$N=4500\text{rpm}$$

$$T=78\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$$

$$n=4$$

$$k=0.5$$

$$P_m= 5 \text{ bar}$$

$$L=110 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$$

$$d=80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$$

$$A = \frac{\pi}{4} d^2$$

$$A = \frac{\pi}{4} (80 \times 10^3)^2$$

$$A=5.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$$

$$BP = \frac{2\pi NT}{60 \times 1000}$$

$$BP = \frac{2 \times \pi \times 4,500 \times 78}{60 \times 1000}$$

$$BP = 36.75 \text{ kW}$$

$$IP = nkPmLAN \times \frac{10}{6}$$

$$IP = 4 \times 0.5 \times 5 \times 110 \times 10^{-3} \times 5.2 \times 10^{-3} \times 4500 \times \frac{10}{6}$$

$$IP = 42.9 \text{ kW}$$

$$FP = IP - BP$$

$$FP = 42.9 - 36.75$$

$$FP = 6.15 \text{ kW}$$

$$n_m = \frac{BP}{IP} \times 100$$

$$n_m = \frac{36.75}{42.9} \times 100$$

$$n_m = 85.56\%$$

$$n_{ith} = \frac{IP}{m_f \times CV}$$

$$n_{ith} = \frac{42.9}{0.00229 \times 43000}$$

$$n_{ith} = 43.56\%$$

$$n_{bth} = \frac{BP}{m_f \times CV}$$

$$n_{bth} = \frac{36.75}{0.00229 \times 43000}$$

$$n_{bth} = 29.47\%$$

$$ISFC = \frac{m_f}{IP}$$

$$ISFC = \frac{0.00229}{42.9} \times 3600$$

$$ISFC = 0.192 \text{ kg/kWh}$$

$$BSFC = \frac{m_f}{BP}$$

$$BSFC = \frac{0.00229}{36.75} \times 3600$$

$$BSFC = 0.224 \text{ kg/kWh}$$

When Hydrogen is added

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Moles of N}_2 \text{ in air} &= \text{Moles of O}_2 \times (79\% \text{ in air } 21\%) \\ &= 3.762 \text{ Moles of N}_2 \end{aligned}$$

Number of moles of air = 4.763 Moles of air

Weight of O₂ = 32g

Weight of N₂ = 108.33g

Weight of H₂ = 4g

Number of mole of H₂ = 9.130 Moles

The percentage of the combustion chamber occupied by hydrogen for a stoichiometric mixture 29.6%

$$\begin{aligned} BP &= \frac{2\pi NT}{60 \times 1000} \\ BP &= \frac{2 \times \pi \times 4,500 \times 91}{60 \times 1000} \\ \mathbf{BP} &= \mathbf{42.88 \text{ kw}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} IP &= nkPmLAN \times \frac{10}{6} \\ IP &= 4 \times 0.5 \times 5.2 \times 110 \times 10^{-3} \times 4500 \times \frac{10}{6} \\ \mathbf{IP} &= \mathbf{44.6 \text{ kw}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} FP &= IP - BP \\ FP &= 44.6 - 42.88 \\ \mathbf{FP} &= \mathbf{1.73 \text{ Kw}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} n_m &= \frac{BP}{IP} \times 100 \\ n_m &= \frac{42.87}{44.66} \times 100 \\ \mathbf{n_m} &= \mathbf{96\%} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} n_{bt} &= \frac{BP}{mf \times cv} \\ n_{bt} &= \frac{42.87}{0.0000021 \times 45100} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{n_{ith}} &= \mathbf{45.26\%} \\ n_{it} &= \frac{IP}{mf \times cv} \end{aligned}$$

$$n_{ith} = \frac{44.60}{0.0000021 \times 45100}$$

$$n_{ith} = 47.15\%$$

$$ISFC = \frac{mf}{IP}$$

$$ISFC = \frac{0.0000021}{42.87} \times 3600$$

$$ISFC = 1.7634 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/kWh}$$

$$BSFC = \frac{mf}{BP}$$

$$BSFC = \frac{0.0000021}{44.66} \times 3600$$

$$BSFC = 1.692 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/kWh}$$

Table 1: Comparison of Performance Parameters

SI No.	Petrol Engine			With Hydrogen		
	Nm	nith	nbth	nm	nith	nbth
1	85.56%	43.56%	29.47%	96%	87.56%	83.94%
2				97%	88.56%	84.31%
3				97.40%	89.14%	85.16%

Figure 1: Variation of different efficiency for varying concentration of hydrogen

Table 2: Engine Specification

Engine Type	In-Line Engine
Displacement	993 cc
Compression Ratio	9.4:1
Transmission Type	Manual
Gear Box	5 Speed
Fuel Type	Petrol
Petrol Mileage ARAI	17.3 kmpl
Bore	80 mm
Stroke	110
Specific Gravity	0.833 Kcal/Kg
No. of Cylinder	4 Cylinders

Table 3: Carbon Cleaning Report

Carbon Cleaning Report						
	Bef ore	After 10min	After 20min	After 30min	Avg.	Performance(%)
CO(%)	0.84	0.62	0.58	0.53	0.57	68.7
HC(ppm)	205	106	105	104	105	51.2
CO2(%)	12.8	12.1	11.2	11.1	11.46	89.6
O2(%)	1.77	4.1	4.26	4.39	4.25	240.1
Nox(ppm)	212	169	170	154	164.3	77.5

Table 4: Fuel Consumption

Fuel Consumption			
	Fuel in ml	Without HHO	With HHO
Trial 1	100 ml	0.9 Km	1.4 Km
Trial 2	200 ml	2.1 Km	2.8 Km
Trial 3	300ml	3.4 Km	4.4 Km

Figure 2: Graph of Distance Travelled vs Fuel Consumed

Table 5: Power output

Engine Speed (rpm)	Petrol Power (kW)	Petrol Power with HHO (kW)	Theoretical Power (kW)
1800	18.00	24	37
2500	25	30	51
3000	32	38	61
3500	38	43	71
4000	42	48	82
4200	40	46	86
4500	38	44	92
5000	35	41	102
5500	30	35	112

Figure 3: Graph of Power output vs Speed of engine

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exploration of hydrogen enrichment technology for petrol engines presents a promising avenue for improving fuel efficiency and reducing emissions. Throughout this study, we have identified and addressed key challenges related to combustion optimization, system integration, safety, cost-effectiveness, regulatory compliance, infrastructure development, public perception, and more. By overcoming these obstacles through collaborative research and innovation, hydrogen-enriched petrol engines hold the potential to play a significant role in achieving a cleaner and more sustainable transportation future.

After adding hydrogen along with the petrol, the power of the engine has increased 17% and the fuel efficiency is increased by 38%.

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